

Compliance discrimination via biomimetic optical tactile sensors and human-like impedance regulation

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Abstract—Endowing robots with biomimetic tactile sensors enhances contact information retrieval. In previous work, we proposed a vision-based approach inspired by human tactile perception to discriminate object compliance with a soft biomimetic tactile optical sensor (TacTip). In this work, we first enhanced the vision-based method by improving the accuracy of the estimation of the initial contact area. Then, we integrated the mechanism of internal muscular regulation (co-contraction) that humans adopt to maximize the information uptake during object compliance probing. To this aim, we used human co-contraction patterns extracted during object softness probing to control a Variable Stiffness Actuator used to actuate the indentation system endowed with the TacTip. The obtained results show that the proposed improvements significantly enhance our model-based approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human touch exhibits remarkable perceptual capabilities due to the interplay between tactile mechanoreceptors, the motor system, and the mechanical properties of the skin. A crucial function of touch is the perception of object compliance, which is gleaned through skin deformation during contact [1].

Replicating human tactile abilities in robots is a complex challenge, but biomimetic approaches provide promising solutions. Particularly, biomimetic soft optical tactile sensors have made notable progress by mimicking the sensitivity and functionality of human touch [2]. Recent advancements have integrated tactile sensors with deep learning techniques to replicate this ability in machines. However, challenges remain in generalizing across diverse tactile interactions due to the complexity of data required for effective training. In our previous work [3], a model-based approach leverages the Contact Area Spread Rate (CASR) paradigm [4], (the contact area growth over increasing force the softer the object is) was introduced to estimate compliance using the TacTip sensor. However, the role of active muscle control in shaping touch perception was not fully explored. Research [5] has shown that humans adjust muscle co-contraction to modulate finger impedance during soft object probing. Particularly, the focus was on the flexo-extension of the index finger, primarily controlled by the metacarpophalangeal (MCP) joint actuated by two antagonistic forearm muscles, i.e. the Flexor

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Fig. 1: Biomimetic Approach Pipeline

Digitorum Superficialis (FDS), and the Extensor Digitorum Communis (EDS). The impedance of this joint increases with the simultaneous activation of the two muscles (co-contraction), enhancing the human ability to perceive soft objects during probing activity.

In this new work, we present two key improvements made to the model: first, an enhancement of compliance estimation by refining the vision algorithm for more accurate initial contact area estimation; second, the integration of human-like muscle co-contraction strategies into the actuation system. In the latter case, muscle impedance patterns from three participants were mapped onto the Variable Stiffness Actuator (VSA), which mimics the agonistic-antagonistic behaviour of human muscles [6], to replicate human muscular dynamics during specimen indentation using TacTip. The results demonstrate significant improvements in reducing compliance estimation error, even for non-perpendicular indentations, and increased sensitivity to varying compliance levels. These findings validate the biomimetic approach, highlighting its potential to improve the adaptability and precision of our robotic system when faced with diverse compliance characteristics encountered during object exploration.

II. METHODS

A. Background

In [3] we used time-to-contact paradigm applied to optical flow from TacTip images to estimate CASR [4], [7] during the indentation of silicone samples. First, we evaluate the contact area corresponding to the measured probing force F_i at the i -th frame as $A_{c_i} = A_{c_0} \exp(\mathcal{D} \text{cum} F_i)$, where A_{c_0} represents the initial area calculated through a vision algorithm, and $\mathcal{D} \text{cum}$ is the summation of the divergence of the dense optical flow in a frame sequence. Then, from the contact area value the CASR $\frac{dA_{c_i}}{dF_i}$, at frame i is computed as $\frac{dA_{c_i}}{dF_i} = \sum_{j=1}^i \frac{A_{c_j} - A_{c_{j-1}}}{F_j - F_{j-1}}$, considering $F_0 = 0$.

B. Improved Vision Algorithm

The new vision algorithm aims to enhance the estimation of the initial contact area by identifying the pins on the

TacTip’s surface that have actually shifted between the static sensor frame and the first frame captured during contact. Specifically, we detect the centroid of pins that show a minimum displacement of three pixels between these frames. This centroid serves as the center of a hexagonal shape, chosen for its efficient coverage of the TacTip’s surface (fig: 1). To estimate the initial contact area, we sum the areas of the hexagons formed by the displaced pins. This particularly enhances the model when the contact is not along the direction normal to the object’s surface [3]. Applying statistical analysis, we verified that the initial area values did not vary significantly with changes in the specimen (minimum p-values: 0.51) but were statistically different with changes in contact direction (worst p-value: $3.1079e - 05$).

C. Human-Like Compliance Exploration

To retrieve the co-contraction profile to be mapped into the VSA [6] we conducted experimental session with 3 right-handed subjects. We asked them to explore along the axis perpendicular to the object while maintaining increasing force (an F/T sensor was placed under the specimen), 5 specimens with different stiffness. The experiments focused on flexion movements of the index finger, whose impedance is modulated by the activation of the FDS and EDC muscles. During the experiments we collected surface electromyography (EMG) measurements. Then we processed the raw data by applying the rectification and smoothing method with the Root-Mean-Square (RMS) processing. Each couple of pre-processed FDS and EDC EMG profiles was summed to obtain the co-contraction activity, e.g., muscular impedance [8]. Then the obtained curves were fitted using a logarithmic equation (worst-adjusted R-squared value equal to 0.832). Then, we employed a statistical analysis on the fitted curves to demonstrate that (1) no significant differences in EMG profiles, relative to the same specimens, exist among the subjects, (2) different impedance profiles are employed by the participants during the exploration of S_1 , S_3 , and S_5 . Based on that, we mapped the average trend corresponding to S_1 , S_3 , and S_5 , of random subjects, in the stiffness range of the VSA.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The setup shown in 1, is used to perform the experiments. Experiments consist of indenting with the TacTip sensor, along the chosen contact direction (normal axis, 30° and 45° inclination), specimens with different levels of compliance by applying incremental probing force. We consider specimens S_1 , S_3 , and S_5 , which showed statistically significant differences in muscle impedance profiles and the S_2 , from now on denoted as S_{new} , as a new specimen for the stiffness estimation error evaluation. Note that, the impedance profile for S_{new} is obtained through interpolation of the other three obtained profiles (fig. 1). We tested the human-like method involving the VSA with muscle impedance profiles mapped onto the stiffness, by collecting for each specimen and contact direction, data on forces, and TacTip images. Then, we resampled data from experiments averaging force values (recorded at 200 Hz) to match TacTip images (recorded at 20 Hz). To obtain the CASR values, we applied our proposed method using the data from each trial, incorporating the new area estimation strategy. Then, we apply the new area estimation strategy and our proposed method to evaluate the dense optical flow, estimate the initial area, and compute the CASR from the pre-processed data.

IV. RESULTS

Applying the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by a Bonferroni correction, on the obtained CASR curve, we test significant differences in CASR values across the three specimens at different indentation angles. The results revealed a rejection of the null hypotheses, with the worst p-value = 0.0034 for the surface at angles 0° and 30° and p-value = 0.0018 for the surface at 45° .

Then, we applied this approach to a new specimen S_{new} across three contact angles to evaluate its CASR and confirm its classification within the stiffness and CASR scale. Boxplots in fig. 1 illustrate the CASR discrimination for each specimen across indentation angles (30° and 45°), and highlight that the specimens are correctly discriminated based on the fact that the CASR values are higher the softer the object is. Based on the results, we derived the relationship between the evaluated CASR and known stiffness of S_1 , S_3 , and S_5 through exponential fitting that results in an adjusted R-squared of 0.9753 in the worst case. We used this relation, to estimate $K_{S_{new}}$ obtaining an estimation error equal to 3%, 3% and 4% for 0° , 30° , and 45° , respectively.

V. DISCUSSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The current results, demonstrate significant improvements in stiffness estimation using the new vision algorithm and the variable stiffness palpation implemented by leveraging the studied human muscular impedance. Specifically, we observe an estimation error reduction of 3%, 22%, 24% for the three considered indentation angles. Moreover, the human-like approach allows for a marked distinction in the values of $\frac{dA}{dF}$ with respect to the high-stiffness one [3].

Nonetheless, we acknowledge that this model has some limitations that are currently under investigation. Despite this, the results of the new model demonstrate enhanced robustness and adaptability across various exploration conditions, opening promising scenarios for the integrated perception and grasping control of soft deformable objects with miniaturized versions of the TacTip and variable impedance human-inspired robotic hands.

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